

VEHICLE SERVICE MANAGEMENT (VSM) SYSTEM FOR EMO ENTERPRISES

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Background

EMO Enterprises is a service dealer of David Peiris Motor Company (Pvt.) Ltd. Its Service Center mainly provides service and repair facilities for motor bicycles and sells genuine spare parts. All these services are offered only for Bajaj motorbike customers.

Currently, they use a file-based system (manual system) for managing vehicle service operations. When a customer needs to repair his motor bicycle, first he has to fill a document called a “job card” which includes details related to the customer and the vehicle. They do not maintain a separate file of registered customers. However, they issue an invoice for the services they provide and spare parts they sell. Currently, they maintain their stocks in Excel sheets.

System Analysis

Identified Issues

Examination of the current system revealed the following issues.

- No computer-based information system to manage their work.
- No automated inventory control system.
- No centralized database.
- No method to generate the required reports.
- No customer *Reminding* method.
- No easy method for getting information about vehicles serviced

Functional Requirement

There were several functional requirements for the proposed system as specified below.

- Authentication of users
- Insert, update and delete vehicle and customer details

- View customer reports
- Insert, update and delete service information of vehicles
- View reports of services
- Add, update and delete inventory
- Prepare purchase orders
- View inventory reports
- Prepare invoices
- Add inquiries

Objectives for the Proposed System

Based on the systems analysis, an automated Vehicle Service Management (VSM) was proposed and it contained the following objectives.

- To provide an automated solution
- To remove duplication of data
- To increase the inefficiency of operations
- To generate required reports
- To provide the facility for backing up data

System Design

User Interface Design

A user interface was developed to effectively manage the operations of the Service Center and it is illustrated in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Home Interface

Data Design

An ERD, also known as an entity-relationship diagram, was used in database design to graphically illustrate the relationships among people, objects, places, concepts or events within that system. The ERD developed for this system is illustrated in Figure 2.

Figure 2: ER Diagram

Process Design - Use Case Diagram

A use case diagram is used to summarize the details of a system's users (also known as actors) and their interactions with the system. The use case diagram developed for VSM System is illustrated in Figure 3.

Figure 3: Use case diagram for VSM System

System Development

System development activities

System development activities of the VSM system included: building necessary databases, building appropriate and user-friendly interfaces, and the coding of required programs.

Application development tools

Interfaces were created using Scene Builder form and IntelliJ Idea components. Java was used as the main programming language to develop the system. IntelliJ

Idea 2.3.3 IDE was used as the targeted framework of the system. MYSQL was used to build the required databases for the VSM system.

System testing and evaluation effort

The testing of the VSM software was done in three steps: unit testing, system testing, and functional testing. VSM software consisted of two main modules: Service Management and Inventory Control modules. Each module consisted of several individual programs.

Unit testing was performed on those individual programs. At the end of coding, each program was tested for bugs and identified bugs were fixed to ensure the smooth running of the individual programs.

Once it was confirmed that all the individual programs were running without any issue, the system testing was done to identify any bugs when the system was run as a whole. At this point also, several bugs were encountered, and the necessary modifications were done to fix those issues.

Finally, the functional testing was performed focusing on two main processes: the authentication process and customer data entry process. During this process, necessary test cases were identified, test data were written, test cases were executed, and finally, the actual outcome was compared with the expected outcome. Functional testing also revealed several bugs in the system, and they were fixed to ensure that the VSM system was running properly as expected.

Conclusion

Summary

Service Center of EMO Enterprises has run with a manual system for managing their operations. They had faced many issues with this system. Therefore, the overall objective of this project was to develop an automated system as a solution for the existing issues. Consequently, a detailed analysis was done to identify and go deep into the existing issues and identify their requirements. Next, a system was carefully designed using design tools including ERD and Use Case diagrams.

Finally, the automated software solution identified as “VSM System” was developed using many development tools.

Achievements

The objectives were achieved, set at the beginning of the project by developing an automated system which could fulfil the requirements of users at EMO Enterprises. The system testing revealed that “VSM System” eliminated the issues identified in the existing manual system. Especially, the automated system leads to efficient transactions with customers. The data stored in the system helps the company to generate various useful reports and to provide better customer service. Overall, this leads to increased customer satisfaction and customer loyalty towards the company, helping them to attract more customers and retain them in the long run.

Limitations

The VSM system is a standalone software system which runs only on computers where the system is installed. Further, the system can only handle operations related to “service management” and “inventory control”.

Future Enhancements

The VSM system can be further improved as a web-based application so that both the company and the customers are benefitted. A web-based application can result in further improving customer service and satisfaction. Also, the system can be further enhanced by incorporating the other modules which have not been incorporated into the present system.

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